

SHORT COMMUNICATIONS

Reactions of Titanium and Zirconium Tertiary
Tutoxides with Acetyl Bromide

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Bradley *et al*¹⁻³ have shown that in the reactions of acetyl chloride with titanium and zirconium tertiary alkoxides the replacement of first tertiary alkoxide group with chlorine is facile but later, the reaction becomes slow and further substitution is difficult even under reflux with excess of acetyl chloride—a conclusion based on the analyses of metal and chlorine only. This behaviour was attributed to be due to steric hindrance caused by the bulky tertiary alkyl groups.

In our earlier publications³⁻⁷ on the reactions of metal tertiary butoxides with acetyl halides it has been shown that the reactions in the beginning proceed in a simple manner yielding halide tertiary butoxides :

TABLE 1

Reactions of Titanium Tertiary Butoxide with Acetyl Bromide

Reaction mixture	Molar ratio	Conditions of the experiment*	Nature of the product §	Analysis						
				Ti%	Found Br%	Br/Ti	Required Alk. eq. in moles	Ti%	Required Br%	Alk. eq. in moles
Ti(OBU ^t) ₄ (4.10 g) CH ₃ COBr (1.48 g) in benzene (15.5 g)	1 : 1	Refluxed 100°/2 hrs.	Colourless solid turns yellow on keeping, b.p. 91-92°/1.5 mm (4.23g) TiBr(OBU ^t) ₃	13.8	23.1	1.0	1.0	13.80	23.03	1.0
Ti(OBU ^t) ₄ (1.11 g) CH ₃ COBr (0.80 g) in benzene (9.80 g)	1 : 2	Room temperature 30°/36 hrs.	Yellow solid (1.03 g) TiBr _{1.3} (OAc) _{0.7} (OBU ^t) ₃	14.8	31.0	1.3	2.0	14.12	30.62	2.0
Ti(OBU ^t) ₄ (2.85 g) CH ₃ COBr (3.10 g) in benzene (16.4 g)	1 : 3	Room temperature 30°/40 hrs.	Yellow solid (2.43 g) Ti ₂ OBr _{1.5} (OAc) _{3.5} (OBU ^t) _{1.5} 0.6BU ^t OAc	16.5	21.7	0.8	2.4	16.35	21.81	2.4
Ti(OBU ^t) ₄ (2.86 g) CH ₃ COBr (4.13 g) in benzene (15.8 g)	1 : 4	Refluxed 100°/2 hrs.	Yellow solid (2.13 g) Ti ₂ OBr _{1.5} (OAc) _{4.5}	19.6	23.8	0.75	2.9	19.27	24.11	3.0
Ti(OBU ^t) ₄ (2.91 g) CH ₃ COBr (3.25 g) in benzene (13.9 g)	1 : 5	Refluxed 100°/2 hrs.	Yellow solid (2.13 g) Ti ₂ OBr _{1.5} (OAc) _{4.5}	19.4	25.3	0.79	2.9	19.20	25.60	3.0

* The reactions were initiated at a cold bath (0-5°) temperature.

Refluxing was done at a bath temperature of 100°.

§ These are empirical formulae (except TiBr(OBU^t)₃ which is a distillable solid) calculated on the basis of analytical data. Similar remarks would apply for the other tables also.

1. D. C. Bradley, D. C. Hancock and W. Wardlaw, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 2773.
2. D. C. Bradley, F. M. A. Halim, R. C. Mehrotra and W. Wardlaw, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 4609.
3. R. C. Mehrotra and R. A. Misra, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1964, 42, 717.
4. R. C. Mehrotra and R. A. Misra, *Jour Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 44, 37.
5. R. C. Mehrotra and R. A. Misra, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1965, 3, 500.
6. R. C. Mehrotra and R. A. Misra, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 43.
7. R. C. Mehrotra and R. A. Misra, *Indian J. Chem.*, (In Press).

With subsequent replacement of tertiary butoxide group by halogen, the electrophilic nature of metal also increases and the halide tertiary butoxides finally react with tertiary butyl acetate (a side product) giving products with metal-acetoxy bonds:

We have also furnished proof for the above by carrying out the reactions between metal halides and tertiary butyl acetate.

In the reactions of titanium butoxide with acetyl bromide (table 1) in equimolecular proportion, a distillable product, $TiBr(OBu^t)_3$ is obtained:

Further additions of acetyl bromide in higher molar ratios yielded acetoxy products which finally appear to decompose into basic acetate derivatives. The formation of such basic acetates of titanium has already been reported in a number of other publications^{6, 8, 9} by Pande and Mehrotra. The corroboration of above facts

TABLE 2

Reaction of Titanium Tetrabromide with Tertiary Butyl Acetate

Reaction mixture	Molar ratio	Conditions of the experiment*	Nature of the product	Analysis							
				Found				Required			
				Ti%	Br%	Br/Ti	Alk. eq. in moles	Ti%	Br%	Alk. eq. in moles	
$TiBr_4$ Bu^tOAc in benzene (11.5 g)	(1.32 g) (1.26 g)	1 : 3 Overnight (22°)	Yellow solid (1.51 g) $Ti_2OBr_{3.6}(OAc)_{3.4}$ $2Bu^tOAc$	12.0	35.8	1.8	3.0	12.39	37.18	3.0	
$TiBr_4$ Bu^tOAc in benzene (15.4 g)	(0.87 g) (0.99 g)	1 : 4 Overnight (22°)	Yellow solid (0.97 g) $Ti_2OBr_{3.3}(OAc)_{3.8}$ $1.6Bu^tOAc$	13.2	35.8	1.6	2.9	13.33	35.58	3.0	
$TiBr_4$ Bu^tOAc in benzene (20.5 g)	(1.02 g) (15.5 g)	1 : excess Refluxed 100°/3 hrs.	White solid (1.2 g) $Ti_2O(OAc)_6$	20.3	—	—	3.0 OAc 75.8%	20.55	—	3.0 OAc 76.00%	

* The reactants were mixed at a cold bath (0–5°) temperature.

has been furnished by the reactions of titanium tetrabromide with tertiary butyl acetate (Table 2) in which case also the oxyacetates of titanium are the final products. The reactions in lower molar ratios have not been given (table 2) because $TiBr_4$ and $Ti(OAc)Br_3$ catalyse some side reactions yielding some polymeric products⁵.

8. K. C. Pande and R. C. Mehrotra, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1957, **290**, 95 ; **291**, 97.

9. K. C. Pande and R. C. Mehrotra, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1959, **8**, (No. 4) 64, 235.

The reaction between zirconium tertiary butoxide and acetyl bromide (Table 3) in equimolar ratio appears to be slow but with further replacement side-reactions occur resulting in the formation of acetate derivatives.

TABLE 3
Reactions of Zirconium Tertiary Butoxide with Acetyl Bromide

Reaction mixture	Molar ratio	Conditions of the experiment*	Nature of the product	Analysis							
				Found			Required		Alk. eq. in moles		
				Zr%	Br%	Br/Zr	Zr%	Br%	Alk. eq. in moles		
Zr(OBu ^t) ₄ (2.90 g) CH ₃ COBr (0.94 g) in benzene (15.5 g)	1 : 1	Refluxed 100°/2 hrs.	White solid (2.79 g) ZrBr _{0.8} (OBu ^t) _{3.4}	24.7	12.2	0.55	23.54	12.37	0.6		
Zr(OBu ^t) ₄ (1.85 g) CH ₃ COBr (1.19 g) in benzene (9.80 g)	1 : 2	Room temperature 30°/36 hrs.	Yellowish white solid (2.24g) ZrBr _{1.4} (OAc) _{0.6} (OBu ^t) _{3.0} 0.7Bu ^t OAc	19.6	23.4	1.4	19.57	23.96	2.0		
Zr(OBu ^t) ₄ (2.03 g) CH ₃ COBr (1.96 g) in benzene (12.5 g)	1 : 3	Refluxed 100°/2 hrs.	White solid (2.02 g) ZrBr _{0.9} (OAc) _{2.3} (OBu ^t) ₃	28.4	18.2	0.8	25.48	17.85	3.0		
Zr(OBu ^t) ₄ (1.80 g) CH ₃ COBr (2.3 g) in benzene (15.3 g)	1 : 4	Refluxed 100°/2 hrs.	Yellow solid (1.77 g) ZrBr(OAc) _{3.5} (OBu ^t) _{0.5}	25.6	22.6	1.0	25.68	22.50	3.0		
Zr(OBu ^t) ₄ (1.08 g) CH ₃ COBr (2.07 g) in benzene (11.6 g)	1 : 6	Refluxed 100°/2 hrs.	Yellow solid (1.05 g) ZnBr(OAc) ₃	26.8	24.8	1.0	26.20	22.96	3.9		

* The reactions were initiated at a cold bath (0–5°) temperature. Refluxing was done at a bath temperature of 100°.

EXPERIMENTAL

All glass apparatus was used with precautions to exclude moisture. Titanium and zirconium tertiary butoxide and tertiary butyl acetate were prepared and purified as described earlier^{5,6}. Acetyl bromide was carefully fractionated and the fraction collecting at 76° was used. Titanium tetrabromide (Found: Ti, 13.1; Br, 87.5%. Calcd. for Ti Br₄: Ti, 13.03; Br, 86.97%) was a Dr. Theoder Schuhardt (Germany) product and was used without further purification.

Analyses of the compounds for the determination of metals, bromide, and alkali equivalents (acetoxy+halogen) were carried out by the standard methods as reported elsewhere^{5,6}.

The reactants in different molar ratios were mixed in benzene in a cold bath (0–5°). The reaction mixture was either kept at the room temperature or refluxed for

a specified period of time, when an insoluble product separated out of the solvent. Products were dried under reduced pressure. Experimental details are tabulated (tables 1, 2 and 3) for abbreviation.

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